

A Review of Instructional Strategies for Enhancing Learner Performance Across Diverse Learning Styles with Emphasis on the Afghan Context

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Abstract

This review investigated pedagogical approaches for improving learner performance, focusing on multifaceted learning styles in language education. Based on twenty recent studies, it reviews prominent models such as Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences, VARK, Dunn and Dunn, field-dependent/field-independent, and the Unified Learning Style Model (ULSM). The literature demonstrates that learners differ in how they process information stemming from cognitive, affective, social, biological, and instructional factors. Noticing these differences helps learner-centered teaching, enhances engagement, and strengthens autonomy. The review also discusses instructional differentiation and flipped learning as approaches that captivate learners through multiple modal approaches beyond traditional learning-style-based teaching. Notwithstanding criticisms about the validity of learning styles and the meshing hypothesis, the paper claimed that flexible instruction that embraces different learning styles remains valuable. In the Afghan context, where lecture-based teaching is conventional, using diverse strategies aligned with learner differences can improve involvement and performance.

Keywords: *Learning Styles, Learner-Centered Instruction, Flipped Learning, Differentiated Teaching, Language Education.*

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Introduction

One of the key factors in the learning-teaching process is often overlooking the learner. Indeed, as a teacher, it is important to know who the learners are and how they would learn. It would seem that individuals learn in different ways. Some of them might be at ease when exposed to a lecture-

type explanation. While others would learn easily by watching visual aids, such as pictures, gestures, and videos. Some learners would get the lesson by participating in a group, using their hands or other body parts. For instance, playing a game would pave the way for even the reluctant students to participate in the class activities and be engaged in the learning process. These differences are called learning styles. Unsal (2018) asserted that individuals learn through diverse favored treatments called learning styles. To be in line with the author, learning style is a particular way of learning that students apply while learning. Therefore, identifying students' learning styles is a necessary issue that helps teachers manage the learning process.

Moreover, as the learner is a focal point in the process of teaching-learning, everything related to the learners is important as well. Therefore, learning style is one of the key factors influencing the learning process. Generally, teachers are acting as a transmitter of information to the learners, and learners are receiving whatever is being transferred to them without productivity and reflection. It means that the teachers do not consider who the learners are, how they are going to learn, and what types of personalities and learning styles they have. Even though many research articles have been published in the area of learning styles and their identification, the researchers have not found any related literature about how teachers should teach considering students' different learning styles. Decidedly, they have attempted to conduct this research to fill the aforementioned gap in the area of teaching. Thus, they have tried to find some solutions to these problems by conducting a literature review in this field, and this research aims to help novice and inexperienced teachers consider individual differences and learning styles while teaching in class. Moreover, an attempt is made to provide an opportunity for learners to identify their learning styles and select a facilitating route to their learning objectives so that they develop autonomous and/or lifelong learning. As a result, this research is conducted to contribute to the education community and facilitate the learning process, which has permanently emphasized by the recent methodologists.

Learning Styles of Language Learners

Among many influencing factors associated with second language learning, one of them is the learner, which impacts the process of learning to a great extent. Farhady and Delshad (2014) asserted that the learner has often been marginalized throughout the process of learning. They pointed out how important the needs and desires of a learner are in language learning. Concerning the authors' ideas, it is worth mentioning that learners are the central points in the process of learning. Issues such as who the learner is, how he/she learns the language, what type of cognitive style or personality type he/she has, and many other what's and how's exist to be taken into account during the teaching-learning process. Therefore, learning style, which is related to the learners' needs and preferences, is one of the most significant points to be considered in the process of teaching and learning. Learning styles imply the particular ways through which one can better learn. In other words, individuals learn in a particular selected way, which is called a learning style.

Rinekso (2021) mentioned that the theory of multiple intelligences was first proposed by Gardner in 1993. He presented a model based on which learners are sorted into 8 groups according to human intelligence. The categories include linguistic learners, logical/mathematical learners, musical learners, spatial/visual learners, kinesthetic learners, interpersonal learners, intrapersonal learners, and naturalistic learners. Gardner believed that linguistic learners like to obtain information verbally, so they are more interested in text reading and talking to someone to get information. Also, logical learners are believed to be involved in quantity-based learning preferences. In addition, musical learners tend to gain knowledge and information via sounds and identify sound elements easily. As well, visual learners learn better when exposed to perceptible objects like pictures, gestures, videos, and so on. Kinesthetic learners prefer to go beyond their

comfort zones and engage in movement-based learning situations. Interpersonal learners are very keen on knowing other people's feelings, while intrapersonal learners prefer self-conception and self-realization. Lastly, naturalistic learners are interested in natural studies such as animals and plants. Then, the overall idea of learning styles goes beyond how individuals learn in a particular way, called multiple intelligences.

Furthermore, Rinekso (2021) cited four types of learning styles, entitled 'Sensory Preferences', 'Personality Types', 'Desired Degree of Generality', and 'Biological Differences'. These characteristics are the signals and routes through which different students choose how well they learn. These learning styles vary in each person. The author further cited that learning preferences are not negated by each other. In other words, the same learner with a preferred learning style might have some other learning styles, but one of them will be more dominant than the others. For instance, a visual learner can learn via listening to a lecture or by movement, but he/she will learn well when exposed to a visual environment. Thus, learning styles are intersecting each other as one of them is stronger. Learners with more than one learning style seem to have multiple learning styles, which are called multi-styled learners. Unsal (2018) noted that learning styles in language learning are visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and multi-styled, and he found that most of the language learners are visual learners. Therefore, language learning is influenced by different factors, one of which is learning preferences, so teachers should consider learning modalities while learning. Also, it was highlighted that one of the vastly approved learning style models is the one presented by Dunn and Dunn (Unsal, 2018; Rinekso, 2021). He proved that the learning process is affected 'environmentally', 'effectively', 'sociologically', 'physiologically', and 'psychologically'.

Truthfully, the aforementioned factors strongly impact the process of learning. The environmental factor is related to the situation and context in which learning happens. For instance, some subordinating factors of the environment are sounds, temperature, seating, and many more. Likewise, affective factor includes enthusiasm for learning, commitment to learning, and some other subfactors that emotionally affect the learning process. Besides, the social element implies the norms and implications associated with the social aspects of the learning context. For example, the viewpoints of people toward language learning and expressing oneself are some social factors of learning. In addition, physiological factor includes the need for food and drink, as some learners are comfortable having chocolate while learning. However, some others will never bear such sort of actions during the learning. In the same way, psychological domains bring another learning style forward as some learners may act as reflective, while others may have another distinctive learning preference.

Concurrently, Chen and Chang (2014) explained that in a miscellaneous group, both serialists and holists performed well. Further, the implication of the research indicated that the holists actively engaged in collaborative learning and gained higher scores. Rather, the serialists tended to engage in individual learning, so their performances were weaker.

Additionally, Ginting (2017) stated that learning styles and the learners' ways of thinking are correlated with each other. He pointed to four ways of thinking: 'concrete sequential', 'abstract sequential', 'abstract random', and 'concrete random'. He also claimed that each of these ways of thinking is related to one or more learning styles. 'Concrete sequential' is believed to be more punctual, disciplined, and gain perfection. Such a learner always needs facts while doing and completing something. Also, 'abstract sequential' is said to be logical and analytic. Learners with such a way of thinking are so determined and resourceful that they always try to know if something is true. As well as 'abstract random', it seems to be emotionally sensitive and respectful. Such a sort of learner tends to be alone and is a good listener. He/she likes the exactness of the events and always tries to differentiate the ideas from each other. Besides, 'concrete random' is considered to

be treated spontaneously, and of course, he/she is an independent learner. Also, they are time-bound.

Natividad and Batang (2018) described that learners will learn through different ways of learning. The authors further stated that most of the college students were auditory learners. More importantly, it has been indicated that learning styles vary according to different learning profiles such as course, ethnicity, age, sex, and so on. For instance, it was indicated that late adolescent students are eager to learn through interaction and authentic activities, but as they grow older, they prefer to learn by listening to lectures and discussions. Even though sex is one of the factors that highly influence learning styles, the study revealed that both males and females prefer to study based on auditory, kinesthetic, and tactile learning styles. Besides, culture and ethnicity are also highly influential, and it was described that students with different cultures and ethnicities have had different learning styles.

As a result, there are various learning styles in the field of second language learning, and they are correlated to the ways of thinking. It is said that 'Concrete Sequential learners tend to use visual style, and 'abstract Sequential' learners would like to use reading and auditory style, while

'abstract Random learners desire to use visual and kinesthetic style, and 'concrete random' learners are more auditory learners. Therefore, students' various learning styles and ways of thinking are very influential, and teachers should identify them to provide a student-centered learning environment. This way, the learners will be engaged in the learning process, and it certainly leads to autonomous learning. To lead students into autonomous learning, it is the teacher who provides them with opportunities to express themselves, reflect on their potential, and put their learning into practice.

Factors Associated with Learning Styles

Farhady and Delshad (2014) noted that some important factors affect language learning and teaching. These factors include cognitive factors, affective factors, personality factors, sociocultural factors, biological factors, and instructional factors. Cognitive factors are the unique way of thinking, remembering, and perceiving. In other words, it is the individual style through which an individual learner processes learning. Cognitive factors, in turn, break into various parts like background knowledge, cognitive style, aptitude, and intelligence. These factors influence individual learners' performance differently. For example, a learner may have expanded background knowledge regarding a specific topic, while another learner might face the topic for the first time. A specific learner would have a special intelligence in a particular field, whereas the other learner's intelligence would be different from the first one. In addition, affective factors are considered to be influential in the process of learning. Factors such as introversion and extroversion, motivation, attitude, belief, and emotion come under the umbrella of affective factors. For instance, someone may have full motivation for learning, but others may need to be motivated to learn. Thus, affective factors affect the process of learning a great deal. Besides, personality plays a key role in learning and acquisition. It refers to elements like self-esteem, inhibition, risk-taking, empathy, and anxiety. They impact an individual's learning differently. Subsequently, socio-cultural, biological, and instructional factors in turn influence learning/acquisition in different ways.

Lightbown and Spada (2013) came to the same conclusion, as they believe that learning style is related to the different factors that expose individuals to different ways of learning. The authors classified the learning styles as 'field-independent' and 'field-dependent' or serialist and holistic. Serialist implies a type of learner which tend to separate the details from the whole. Considering the fact, serialists analyze an issue with all its elements and particles. However, the holistic learner

is said to have a general perspective on the issues. Such sorts of learners see things more generally. In other words, holistic learners try to have a greater picture of the issues by over-viewing. Concerning learning style, the authors included more and more factors such as individual differences, learners' beliefs, ethnic group tendencies, age, sex, instruction, motivation, and many more. These factors are deemed to be the various elements on which students learn in various ways. Therefore, it is suggested that teachers maintain a balance between the learners' preferences and instructional methods, as Individual differences might be the most influential factor that makes the job of teaching more and more difficult.

Learning Styles Recognition as a Step in Moving Toward a Learner-Centered Approach

Students' engagement in the learning process is an underlying point that empowers the spirit of the learning-teaching procedure. Contemporarily, the methodologists and researchers believe that learning will be effective if it engages students and makes them interact within the learning-teaching context. In harmony with the other factors influencing students' engagement, learning style is one of the considerable elements that is discussed in the current research. Payaporn and Payaporn (2020) noted that recognizing students' learning styles will lead to student-centered teaching. He further mentioned that most of the learners have multiple learning styles, and among the individual learners' styles, most of them were kinesthetic learners. Regarding the explorations in this field, it is suggested that teachers should attempt to identify students' learning styles and utilize various methodologies aligned with different learning styles. For instance, using visual aids, pictures, and videos will involve visual learners in the lesson and provide them with an opportunity to express themselves comfortably. Also, for auditory learners, a lecture, discussion, and presentation will create a context through which they would be at ease. Likewise, engaging kinesthetic learners in class activities, actions, games, and activities with movements will turn the class into the most delightful place for them. Learning styles-based teaching paves the way for the learners to self-conception and self-realization, so they know how to learn. Learning how to learn is a path via which students tend to improve autonomous learning. In this way, the teachers may act as facilitators, which is the main functionality of a teacher within the communicative approaches. As a result, effective teaching strategies, materials, and approaches should be applied to cover different learning styles.

Flipped Instruction as a Progressive Alternative to Learning Style-Based Teaching

Recently, the implications of flipped learning have been broadly discussed by researchers. Some researchers believe that it is an interactive way of learning inside the class, but others might have a widely expanded definition of flipped learning. Khan and Ibrahim (2017) explained that, unlike traditional learning, inverted learning is a more communicative and interactive group work and computerized learning that helps the learners enhance their language learning skills. Based on flipped class strategies, EFL learners are provided with an opportunity to express themselves, solve problems, and engage in learning. Flipped learning (FL) in comparison with traditional learning is more beneficial since it diversely engages different sorts of learners with various learning styles. Along with the self-efficacy of flipped learning strategies, it serves to move from theory into practice by providing empirical learning experiments. Further, the research indicated that using flipped teaching strategies made students learn equally without considering their learning preferences. Tadayonifar and Entezari (2020) indicated that researchers lately have been searching

to find a new academic manner to manage classes with different learning styles, and they found flipped learning as an influential pedagogy that involves the learners regardless of some influential factors like personality types, psychological factors, affective aspects, and many more. Sincerely, flipped learning strategies fit different classes due to their cross-breeding nature. Thus, it is a step toward teaching beyond learning styles. It certainly encompasses many diverse learning modalities and provides the learners with the opportunity to engage in an active learning process and learn at their own pace, inside and outside the class. The author also came to the conclusion that flipped teaching strategies improve students' learning outcomes, and the visual and kinesthetic learners were, in turn, the highest and lowest successful learners using flipped teaching strategies. Additionally, it revealed that speaking was mostly empowered throughout the flipped learning class, but writing showed lower improvement than speaking. Overall, flipped learning is an effective and innovative approach.

In addition to what has already been said, Kim (2017) found that flipped teaching strategies not only improve interaction and active learning but also pave the way for deep understanding, comprehensive content, personal engagement, and so on. He further emphasized that flipped learning enhances students' skills of communication and leads to a collaborative and cooperative learning atmosphere. Also, it paves the way for the learners to improve their mutual interaction with their colleagues and instructors, and it builds a positive rapport between the learners and the professors. However, he pointed out some limitations that are caused by the flipped learning strategies. For example, a great deal of time is required to prepare before the class, so some of the learners are reluctant to spend such a great amount of time preparing for the class. Besides, some of the learners worried about the implementation of flipped learning in every subject, as the author in his studies revealed that, since the idea of flipped learning is a recently invented pedagogy, it needs a step-by-step implementation.

In another experimental research, which was conducted by Nwokeji and Holmes (2017), the performances of the learners were compared considering the preferred learning style in both traditional and flipped classes. As indicated in the research, in the flipped class, the logical learning style was considered the preferred learning style. Logical learners are those kinds of learners who tend to engage in discussion and argument to develop their perception of the knowledge. They are said to have high performance, generally in-class participation, doing homework, and obtaining high marks in the exam. Nwokeji and Holmes concluded;

This finding is easily explained by the analogy: God gave humans two (2) eyes and one (1) mouth-Visual learners, compared to God giving humans one (1) brain and one (1) mouth-Logical learners. The visual learner will want to observe longer, and then speak/interact. The logical learner will want to discuss /argue sooner to develop their understanding (p. 6).

Based on the research indication, the logical learning style is considered an effective learning preference that impacts the students' performances to a great extent. Therefore, flipped learning strategies are very influential in the learners' performances.

Differentiated Instruction Based on Learner Style Variability

Within the class, it is too difficult to engage every individual in the process of learning, so it needs a pedagogy that stimulates the learners with different characteristics, learning styles, and preferences to be involved in the class. Salam, Socarti, and Arifin (2020) mentioned that different learners would learn by utilizing various learning strategies. For instance, visual learners tend to learn better through reading and note-taking. Therefore, the authors suggested two types of strategies: the cognitive strategy and the compensation strategy. In the cognitive strategy, the learners are involved in reading and writing. In other words, they prefer to learn by reading and

writing rather than listening to verbal lectures, discussions, and many more. On the other hand, based on the compensation strategy, the learners should be provided with the situation to guess from different clues, and it is mostly applicable in listening. In another research, Chen and Chang (2014) explained that learning behaviors seemed to be improved in holists. In a precise way, they are more creative, communicative, and responsive, regardless of whether they are individual or collaborative learners they are. Furthermore, it is suggested that for the learners to perform well, miscellaneous groups should be implemented for their engagement in the process of learning. For example, in a situation where needed, individual learning should be applied. Rather, in some other situations, it might be suggested to use collaborative learning.

Emphasizing the idea of learning preferences consideration, the learning styles of the learners are grouped into four categories: reflectors, theorists, pragmatists, and activists (Churngchow et al 2020; Rinekso, 2021). They stressed that different learning styles should be considered, and individual preferences and desires should be taken into account to get an optimal outcome. It was suggested that the reflectors provide updated materials and authentic situations in which they can explore new knowledge and gain more benefits. As well, for the theorists, it was suggested that they should be provided with lots of beneficial materials and activities, project-based learning, and a large body of background knowledge to overcome limitations and get an acceptable outcome. Likewise, pragmatists prefer to learn better when exposed to situations in which hands-on activities and experience are provided, and instructors act as facilitators. Pragmatists tend to learn practically by doing and prefer to be autonomous learners rather than being dependent on the teacher. Also, activists like to be provided with more instructional support rather than verbal lectures. They are eager to work in groups and be provided with facilities to go ahead at their own pace. Eventually, the four types of learners have different learning preferences.

Durmus and Guven (2020) discussed the relationship between the teachers' teaching preferences and the students' learning preferences and found that both students and teachers possess their own learning and teaching styles. The researchers further suggested that both students and teachers should be aware of their learning and teaching styles. On the other hand, using various techniques and strategies during teaching different courses made a positive impact on the language teachers and expanded their skills and experience (Aydin, 2017; Drums & Guven, 2020). As using different methodologies beyond learning preferences reflects the teachers' expanded skills and high level of training, it is suggested that the teachers get teaching training to meet students' pedagogical needs.

Halif et al. (2020) declared that the learners' motivation is influential in the relationship between the learners' learning styles and classroom engagement. The authors further stressed that the visual learning style is the most influential in-class engagement. In other words, the visual learners are more actively engaged in the class. Based on the findings, the motivation elements affect the relationship between learning styles and learning engagement, so teaching implications have been suggested for teachers to apply in their classrooms for more engagement.

On the other hand, the learners' motivation is very influential in their learning performances. The more the learners are prompted and motivated, the better they will learn and perform. It is said that the learners' motivation relies on some factors like the teachers' motivation and skills, interpersonal relationships with their colleagues, good rapport with the instructors, and many more. Based on these implications, the teachers are to use different methods of teaching as well as strategies to create motivation and enhance the learners' learning performances. For example, teachers should use task-based learning, group projects, technology-based learning, and many other methods to engage the learners in the process of learning. Meanwhile, the teachers should try to maintain a balance between the learners' learning styles and their pedagogy within their teaching.

Concurrently, Kim and Kim (2014) discussed that visual learning seems to have the greatest impact on the learners' performances. It means those learners with visual learning styles are more active

and proficient in learning the English language. Also, the research exhibited that there is a significant correlation between the elementary school's second language self and motivated behaviors and their English proficiency. Elementary school students gain more advantages from their self and motivated behaviors for their English language proficiency. However, the junior high school students' English proficiency is indicated to be less influenced by the self and motivated behaviors. Therefore, teachers should provide an opportunity for elementary school students to be self-learners and be motivated to improve their learning outcomes. Rather, for junior high school students, the teachers should try to provide more support to engage them in the process of learning. For the learners to be actively engaged in the process of learning, motivation plays a vital role, so it is the teacher who creates motivation for the learners. Then, the teachers should try their best to consider motivational factors that are effective for enhancing the learners' engagement and performance. Therefore, the research suggested that teachers use technology effectively and a wide variety of methods, techniques, and strategies to engage the learners within the learning process.

Criticism of Learning Styles

Even though it is indicated that learning style is a significant issue in the teaching-learning process, some cons are considered as criticism against the idea of learning style. Rinekso (2021) highlighted that it is undeniable for learners to learn through various preferred ways, but it might be possible for them to be impacted by some other factors. For instance, he clarified that visual and media-based materials certainly provide students with the opportunity to learn better, but it can probably be the impact of media itself that has broadly influenced the education process. The author further argued that the concept of learning style is questionable since the instruments used for assessing students' learning styles are not valid and reliable, and most of the time, the method of instruction meets the learner's preferred way of learning, not the student learns in a different style.

Nevertheless, the author indicated some pedagogical implications for EFL teachers to consider while teaching practice to broaden their perspectives regarding learning style and pave the way for effective learning. Therefore, it is suggested that teachers concentrate on the effective strategies of learning, which will pave the way for more improvements in the field. It would seem fair that instead of devoting lots of time to learning style engagement, the teachers should try to focus on how to teach effectively and efficiently, regardless of learning styles. To do this, the teachers are to consider the following actions: first, they should assess the learners' background knowledge. It would provide an opportunity for the teachers to tailor their instructions based on the learners' background knowledge and interests, and it would certainly lead to a positive outcome and achievement. Secondly, recognizing the learners' necessities and lacks is very significant, as the teachers would realize what inclusion and exclusion are required in the lesson plans and strategies to be implemented in the class. Thirdly, the teachers should put their efforts into providing the learners with diverse teaching methods regardless of their learning preferences. To encompass many different learning styles, the teachers should supply more media and technology-based learning materials for the learners. Subsequently, it is suggested that teachers allow learners to go at their own pace so that put a step forward in moving toward autonomous learning.

In the same vein, Popescu (2009) argued some criticisms against learning styles. He emphasized that there are lots of factors influencing students' ways of learning, so it is not concluded that the learners only learn in some stereotyped particular ways. In other words, not only learning styles but also many other factors seem to be influential in the process of learning. Also, the diversity in learning styles models is another conflicting issue that has led to the theory of learning styles being criticized. As well, lots of overlapping concepts and a lack of an accepted unified classification regarding learning styles decrease its strengths. Furthermore, the lack of reliability and validity of

learning styles assessment instruments would be counted as a criticism in this regard. Lastly, learning style has been criticized, for it only encompasses the traditional and classic methods. With the invention of lots of recent pedagogies for teaching, the theory of learning style is questionable, as the learning styles models were already presented, ignoring technology and media-based learning. Unlike traditional methods, media and technology, or web-based learning include most of the learning styles within them. For instance, in technology-based learning, visual learning materials are attributed to the technological methods parameter rather than to a particular learning preference. Therefore, the learning style is criticized despite the benefits that it has. Although it is still implemented to some extent, the teachers should broaden their views toward learning styles and try to provide more engaging methods and materials for the learners.

As an alternative to learning style, Popescu (2009) proposed a new approach entitled the Unified Learning Style Model (ULSM). The rationale behind choosing this model is concluded in the following points: first, ULSM is said to have more impacts on the process of learning based on different literature review research. Second, it is very easily implemented in the classroom. It means it is not a stereotyped and abstract idea, but it can be put into practice within the classrooms. For instance, kinesthetic learning is not considered or adapted in e-learning-based teaching. Third, it can be recognized from the overt behaviors of the students. Thus, the three reasons are good enough to prove ULSM as a more effective approach than the stereotyped traditional learning styles theories.

The new pedagogy of ULSM is made up of a collection of learning styles associated with practical e-learning-based teaching. Since the traditional scaffolds of learning style exclude technology and e-learning-based teaching, ULSM is suggested as an alternative to the traditional learning style models, and it includes both the traditional and the new approaches simultaneously. This model encompasses perceptual learning style, cognitive learning style, field-dependent vs. field-independent, social strategies, psychological factors, ways of thinking, individual differences, and many more. The advantages of ULSM are predominantly indicated as follows: first, it prevents overlapping concepts, which was a serious problem in traditional learning style models. Second, based on this model, learning styles are not dichotomous. In other words, they do not negate each other. Rather, they intersect each other, so an individual is said to have both a stronger and a weaker learning style simultaneously. Next, a clear and true classification of the learners is considered an advantage to this model. Consequently, this model includes numerous learning styles models without putting lots of burdens on the teachers' shoulders.

However, Felder (2020) argued that learning style criticism considering the 'meshing hypothesis', based on which matching between teacher instruction and student preferences enhances the learning outcome, is a sophistic argument. He emphasized that it is not matching teachers' instruction with the learner's preferences; rather, it is the teachers who should teach in a way that levels their instructions to the learners' preferences. The author argued that learning style is important to consider while designing instruction for many reasons. First, every learning style deals with different skills' characteristics, so it seems helpful to consider this while teaching. Second, it is effective to keep a balance between the instruction methods and students' preferred ways of learning rather than insisting on scaffolding based on our tendencies. Also, the instruction method does not match every individual in the classroom, so except for a few learners whose learning preferences match the teacher's instruction, the others would be marginalized in the process of learning. Finally, balance maintenance covers the learners' needs, lacks, background knowledge, levels, and many other aspects, which in turn are very helpful for teaching success. Therefore, learning style consideration during teaching is much more helpful than trying to just insist on a particular instruction method.

Discussion and Suggestion

Learning is a process to which many different factors are associated. Learning style is one of those important dimensions that would have a very influential role in the learning process. The current research indicates that learning style is an expanded issue that has greatly influenced the learning process. It was outlined in the literature that individuals learn in preferred behavioral patterns, which differentiate their learning styles. For example, a person may learn better through visual aids like gestures, pictures, and video, while another person might learn better through audio, lecture discussions, and many more. In this research, different models of learning styles have been discussed, like multiple intelligences, the VARK model [visual, auditory, reading, and kinesthetic], the Dun and Dun model, and many other relevant models. Also, different associated factors with learning style, such as social, biological, environmental, psychological, and physiological factors, seemed to impact the process of learning. It was also emphasized that learning style recognition would address students' linguistic and communicative competencies, and it would provide them with the opportunity to be autonomous learners. Furthermore, strategies plus recent pedagogies such as flipped learning for teaching based on students' preferences were presented. Eventually, the learning style model was criticized as a classic method, and alternatives were proposed to be implemented practically in the classroom.

To conduct this literature review, about twenty or more articles have been reviewed, considering the research questions. The articles were well-fitted to the research questions. A range of questions, such as what learning style is, how to recognize learning styles, how learning style helps the learners learn better, and how to teach based on students' preferred learning styles, were posed to be answered via reviewing these research articles. The research articles are all updated and closely fit to answer the research questions.

Based on this literature review research, learning styles seem to have a predominant role in the learning process. Even though learning style is discussed broadly by different researchers as a significant theory, critiques have been raised about it, as most researchers believe that learning style is a traditional theory that does not have a place within the recent pedagogies. The critiques were again rejected by most of the proponents of learning style models. Most of the researchers believe that learning style is still promoted among different applied pedagogies. The researchers emphasized that instead of negating learning style theories, it would be better to broaden our perspective toward learning styles and pave the way for effective strategies associated with learning styles to be implemented in the classroom.

Aligned with the researchers, my view toward learning styles is positive. I strongly agree that learning style consideration during teaching would bring remarkable changes regarding the learners' performances. Based on my perspective, even if the learning style is a traditional theory, it would be helpful. In harmony with most researchers, I believe that teachers should put their efforts to keep maintenance between their instruction methods and the learners' preferred ways of learning. This way, the wrong implications of the theory of learning style as a stereotyped and traditional model would be revised to a newer perspective. Although some researchers asserted that the instruction method matches the learners' preferences, I do not agree since the instruction method cannot be leveled to every individual in the classroom.

Rather, it seems to me logical that the teachers' instruction should be in a dynamic way so that it fits every individual's preferred learning style. Therefore, learning style is still a helpful pedagogy.

Relatively, the answers to the research questions were presented in this literature review. Firstly, the concept of learning style has been discussed with its different types. It was indicated that learning style is a particular pattern of preferred behavior or style that makes individuals learn better in response to the learning style. Second, various models of learning styles are discussed to address

the recognition of learning styles. Consequently, some recently invented pedagogy, such as flipped learning and the Unified Learning Style Model (ULSM), was proposed to cover different learning modalities.

In the Afghan context, learning style consideration seems to be very important since individual differences are observed to a great extent. Based on my experience, those students who are moving from one place to another while learning in the classroom are not irregular. Instead, they have a dynamic and kinesthetic characteristic that should be considered while teaching. In my opinion, if Afghan students are exposed to the different teaching methods that include different learning preferences, they would learn better and enhance their performance. As the teaching approaches used in the Afghan context are mostly lecture-based, they just engage a small number of the learners, while the others are excluded. Therefore, Afghan teachers should try to provide more engaging and effective strategies for teaching to improve the learning outcome.

Conclusion

Learners and teachers are the two inseparable elements of learning that play a vital role in the process of learning. The learner, as the main element of learning, is in turn complex. One of the complexities of learners is their learning styles of learning. Concerning their learning styles, a learner may tend to learn based on the visual learning method, whereas another learner might be more at ease to learn better by being exposed to a lecture-based teaching method. Likewise, some other learners will better learn if they are provided with the opportunity to make movements while learning. These and many other styles of learning are considered learners' preferences. Thus, it can be concluded that learning styles or preferences are the unique ways by which students learn better in different ways. Many types of learning modalities have been classified as multiple intelligences, VARK learning style model, Dun and Dun model, field dependent and field independent, ULSM model, and many more. Every model has its pros and cons. The researchers believe that learning style consideration while teaching enhances the learners' performances and leads them towards being autonomous learners.

Even though learning style theory is an effective strategy used to promote learning, some critiques made of it by researchers. The critiques questioned the validity and reliability of the learning styles assessment instruments. As well, some researchers believe that learners do not learn in different ways. Instead, they argued that the instruction method matches the students' learning preferences. The last claim is rejected by most advocates of learning styles, as they believe that the instruction method cannot be matched to every individual in the classroom simultaneously. Rather, they suggest that the teachers should tailor their instruction method to the students' learning styles, and not expect the learners to adapt to the stereotyped instruction method of the teachers.

In a nutshell, some recently invented approaches have been proposed to be implemented to enhance the effectiveness of learning. For instance, flipped learning is a new pedagogy that would help learners learn regardless of their learning preferences. Also, using different effective strategies and materials is very influential. Therefore, learning style is still effective, and it should be considered in the learning process.

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